

Investigation of the conductance, micellization and dissociation behaviour of uranyl caprylate and laurate in mixed organic solvents

Anubhuti Jain* and S. K. Upadhyaya

Department of Chemistry, S. S. L. Jain P.G. College, Vidisha-464 001, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : anubhutijainj@gmail.com

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Abstract : Conductance measurements were employed to determine the critical micellar concentration (CMC), molar conductance at infinite dilution, degree of dissociation, dissociation constant and thermodynamic parameters for dissociation and association processes of uranyl caprylate and laurate in 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide (v/v) mixture. These soaps behave as a weak electrolytes in dilute solutions below the CMC and Debye-Huckel-Onsager's equation is not applicable to these solutions. The thermodynamic parameters indicate that the micellization process is favoured over the dissociation process.

Keywords : Uranyl soaps, critical micellar concentration, micellization, heat of dissociation, free energy.

Introduction

A wide variety of metal soaps find important applications in a number of industries. Their appreciable solubility in organic solvents make them potentially important in technological uses. Application of metallic soaps depends largely on their physico-chemical properties such as physical state, stability, chemical reactivity and solubility in polar as well as non-polar solvents. Several workers¹⁻¹⁴ have used different techniques for studying the preparation, properties and uses of metal soaps. The physico-chemical properties and structure of alkaline earth and transition metal soaps have been thoroughly investigated, however the same is not true with regards to lanthanide and actinide metal soaps.

The present manuscript was initiated with the aim of finding out the nature of micelles formed and the determination of thermodynamic parameters for uranyl soaps in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide mixture (v/v) by conductivity measurements at different temperatures.

Experimental

Preparation of uranyl carboxylates :

The chemicals used were A.R./B.D.H. grade. Uranyl soaps were prepared by the direct methesis of the corresponding potassium soap with a slight stoichiometric ex-

cess of aqueous uranyl acetate solution at 50–60 °C under vigorous stirring. The precipitates were filtered off and washed with doubly distilled water – acetone and dried. The purity of the soaps were checked by elemental analysis, and the results were found in fair agreement with theoretically calculated values.

Sr. No.	Soap	Results of carbon and hydrogen analysis			
		C%		H%	
		Theoretical	Experimental	Theoretical	Experimental
1.	Uranyl caprylate	34.5	34.0	5.3	5.1
2.	Uranyl laurate	43.1	43.3	6.8	6.5

Measurements :

The conductance of solutions was measured with a "Systronics conductivity Bridge 305" and a dipped type conductivity cell (cell constant 1.0 cm⁻¹) with platinised electrode at 25, 30, 35, 40 °C.

Results and discussion

The specific conductance, *k* of the solutions of uranyl caprylate and laurate in 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide mixture (v/v), increases linearly with increasing concentration, *C*. This may have been due to partial dissociation of these soaps in mixed solvent. However, decreases it

with increasing chain-length of the soaps, due to the higher molecular weight and decreasing mobility of anions. The plots of k vs C (Fig. 1) are characterized by a break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soaps indicating the formation of micelles at this concentration. The results show that increase in temperature results in the increase of CMC (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Specific conductance vs concentration plots of uranyl caprylate in 50% benzene and 50% dimethylsulphoxide mixture (v/v).

Table 1. Critical micellar concentration, CMC (g mol L⁻¹) of uranyl caprylate and laurate in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide (v/v) at various temperatures

Name of the soap	CMC × 10 ³ (g mol L ⁻¹)			
	25 °C	30 °C	35 °C	40 °C
Uranyl caprylate	4.75	5.10	5.60	5.80
Uranyl laurate	4.00	4.25	4.75	5.00

The molar conductance, μ of the solutions of uranyl caprylate and laurate decreases with increasing concentration. The decrease in molar conductance may be attributed to combined effects of ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions and may be due to micellization. The plots of molar conductance μ vs square root of concentration ($C^{1/2}$) (Fig. 2) are concave upwards, indicating that these soaps behaves as a weak electrolyte in dilute solutions. The limiting molar conductance (μ_0) cannot be obtained by the usual extrapolating method as the Debye-Huckel-Onsager's equation¹⁵ is not applicable to these solutions.

Fig. 2. Molar conductance vs square root of concentration of uranyl caprylate at different temperatures.

The probable mode of dissociation of these metal soaps in benzene-dimethylsulphoxide may be developed in Ostwald's manner as,

The dissociation constant, K_D can be written as :

$$K_D = \frac{4C^2\alpha^3}{(1 - \alpha)} \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the dilute solutions do not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and the activities of ions can be taken as almost equal to concentration. Thus degree of dissociation, α may be defined by conductance ratio μ/μ_0 , where μ is the molar conductance at a finite concentration, μ_0 is the limiting molar conductance of these ions.

On substituting the value of α and rearranging, eq. (1), the following expression¹⁶ for the dissociation of uranyl soaps can be written as :

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K_D \mu_0^3}{4\mu} - \frac{K_D \mu_0^2}{4} \quad (2)$$

The dissociation constant, K_D , and limiting molar conductance, μ_0 , have been obtained from the slope, $K_D \mu_0^3/4$ and the intercept, $-K_D \mu_0^2/4$ of the linear plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ for dilute soap solutions. The results show that the values of limiting molar conductance increases while the

Table 2. Molar conductance at infinite dilution, μ_0 and dissociation constant, K_D of uranyl caprylate and laurate in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide (v/v) at various temperatures

Name of the soap	25 °C		30 °C		35 °C		40 °C	
	μ_0	$K_D \times 10^6$						
Uranyl caprylate	28.40	4.27	29.80	3.38	35.00	2.47	38.00	1.75
Uranyl laurate	22.10	4.15	27.40	3.25	30.00	2.26	33.80	1.62

dissociation constant decreases with the rise in concentration (Table 2). The decrease in the value of dissociation constant with temperature indicates the exothermic nature of the dissociation of these soaps in a mixture of solvents. The values of dissociation constant, K_D obtained from above said plots were found in agreement with the values determined by using eq. (1) but show a drift at higher concentration which may be due to the failure of Debye-Huckel's activity equation at higher soap concentration.

The heat of dissociation, ΔH°_D , for uranyl caprylate and laurate is determined by using following equation :

$$\log K_D = \frac{-\Delta H^{\circ}_D}{2.303RT} + C \quad (3)$$

The negative values of the enthalpy of dissociation, ΔH°_D , were obtained from the slope of the linear plots of $\log K_D$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 3), suggest that the dissociation process is exothermic in nature. The exothermicity decreases with increasing chain-length of the uranyl soap molecules

Fig. 3. $\log K_D$ vs $1/T$ for uranyl caprylate and laurate.

(Table 3).

The values of change in free energy, ΔG°_D , and standard entropy change, $T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$ for the dissociation process are calculated by using the relationships :

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_D = -RT \ln K_D \quad (4)$$

$$T\Delta S^{\circ}_D = -\Delta H^{\circ}_D - \Delta G^{\circ}_D \quad (5)$$

The calculated values of ΔG°_D and $T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$ are recorded in Table 3. The values of change in free energy, ΔG°_D , increased with increasing temperature whereas the values of standard entropy change, $T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$, decreased.

In case of micellization, when counter-ions are bound to a micelle, the standard free energy change of micellization, ΔG°_M for phase separation model¹⁷⁻¹⁹ is given by the equation :

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_M = 2RT \ln X_{CMC} \quad (6)$$

where X_{CMC} is the CMC expressed in terms of mole fraction and is defined as,

$$X_{CMC} = \frac{n_s}{n_s + n_o} = \frac{n_s}{n_o} \quad (7)$$

Since the numbers of moles of free soap, n_s , are small as compared to the number of moles of solvent, n_o . The negative values of free energy of micellization decreases with increasing temperature and chain-length of the soap.

The standard enthalpy change of micellization, ΔH°_M , for the phase separation model is evaluated as follows :

$$\ln X_{CMC} = \frac{\Delta H^{\circ}_M}{2RT} + C \quad (8)$$

The values of ΔH°_M have been determined from the slope of linear plots of $\ln X_{CMC}$ vs $1/T$. The positive enthalpy for micellization, ΔH°_M , indicates that the association of uranyl caprylate and laurate in 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide mixture (v/v) is endothermic.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of the dissociation and micellization of uranyl caprylate and laurate in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide mixture (v/v) at various temperatures

Sr. No.	Name of the soap	Dissociation (kilo calorie per mole)								ΔH°_D
		25 °C		30 °C		35 °C		40 °C		
		ΔG°_D	$-T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$	ΔG°_D	$-T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$	ΔG°_D	$-T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$	ΔG°_D	$-T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$	
1.	Uranyl caprylate	12.65	36.45	13.59	37.39	14.49	38.29	15.56	39.36	23.80
2.	Uranyl laurate	12.55	39.05	13.49	39.99	14.46	40.96	15.51	42.01	26.50
Sr. No.	Name of the soap	Micellization (kilo calorie per mole)								ΔH°_M
		25 °C		30 °C		35 °C		40 °C		
		$-\Delta G^{\circ}_M$	$T\Delta S^{\circ}_M$	$-\Delta G^{\circ}_M$	$T\Delta S^{\circ}_M$	$-\Delta G^{\circ}_M$	$T\Delta S^{\circ}_M$	$-\Delta G^{\circ}_M$	$T\Delta S^{\circ}_M$	
1.	Uranyl caprylate	27.83	44.23	27.95	44.35	27.98	44.42	28.18	44.58	16.40
2.	Uranyl laurate	28.86	49.02	28.89	49.05	28.90	49.06	28.93	49.09	20.16

The standard entropy change for micellization is calculated as,

$$T\Delta S^{\circ}_M = \Delta H^{\circ}_M - \Delta G^{\circ}_M \quad (9)$$

The micellization of the soaps in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide (v/v) is consistent with $\Delta H^{\circ}_M > 0$, $\Delta G^{\circ}_M > 0$, $T\Delta S^{\circ}_M > 0$, are mentioned in Table 3. However, dissociation of these soaps is consistent with $\Delta H^{\circ}_D > 0$, $\Delta G^{\circ}_D > 0$, $T\Delta S^{\circ}_D > 0$, are mentioned in Table 3. The results are in consistent with other data^{20,21}.

The negative value of free energy of micellization, ΔG°_M , positive value of $T\Delta S^{\circ}_M$ for micellization and positive value of ΔG°_D and negative value of $T\Delta S^{\circ}_D$ for the dissociation indicate that micellization process is favoured over the dissociation process. It may, therefore, be inferred that in a mixture of 50/50 benzene-dimethylsulphoxide (v/v) uranyl caprylate and laurate behave as weak electrolytes. The values of the critical micellar concentration increase with increasing temperature and the micellization process is predominating over dissociation process.

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